

POLITICAL RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS

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Abstract. *This article discusses "Political Rights," which are evolving in line with modern times. It provides detailed information on the role of these rights in society and the various types of political rights.*

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Throughout history, there has never been a time when people did not fight for their rights. The struggle for human rights has given rise to numerous teachings and theories advocating for a dignified life for individuals. The emergence of the state also brought about the concept of law, which has developed alongside the state. One of the thinkers of the Renaissance and an esteemed legal scholar of the East, Burhoniddin al-Margʻinoniy, supported the idea of institutionalizing and ensuring adherence to natural rights for every individual, regardless of whether they are citizens of a particular state. Since then, the approach to state institutions has shifted to focus on serving the interests of individuals and society.

In line with this idea, it is no coincidence that the second section of our Constitution is titled "*The Fundamental Rights, Freedoms, and Duties of Individuals and Citizens*". It is important to emphasize that the rights of individuals and citizens are divided into three groups: personal rights, socio-economic rights, and political rights.

To briefly define the concept of political rights: **POLITICAL RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS** are a group of fundamental constitutional rights of citizens (alongside civil, personal, and economic rights and freedoms). Political rights and freedoms enable participation in the social and political life of the country.

Mahatma Gandhi also remarked on political rights, stating: "*True freedom is not merely the recognition of political rights but also ensuring the opportunity to exercise them*".

What Are Political Rights? Their Importance for Citizens and Society

In today's fast-paced era, the demand for and attention to political rights in human society are increasing. Political rights and freedoms can be defined more comprehensively as follows.

Political Rights and Freedoms. These represent every person's right to participate in the governance of society and the state, as well as their freedom to express opinions, associate, and carry out other political activities. These rights embody the fundamental principles of democracy and form the foundation of the relationship between the state and its citizens.

As mentioned above, political rights are enshrined in **Section 2, Chapter 8** of our Constitution, covering Articles 36 to 40. This demonstrates the attention given to political rights at the state level. When citizens have firm moral and political convictions, they better understand their rights and responsibilities and participate more actively in the social life of the country.

Political Rights Enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

The right to participate in the management of society and the state (Article 36). Citizens have the right to participate directly or through representatives in governing public and state affairs.

The right to participate in meetings, peaceful assemblies, and demonstrations, as stipulated by the laws of Uzbekistan (Article 38). Citizens can demonstrate social activity in these ways.

The right to join trade unions, political parties, and other public associations (Article 39) Citizens may unite in various organizations to represent their interests.

The right to vote and be elected (Article 128). Citizens may take part in elections as voters or candidates, influencing the formation of elected bodies.

The right to submit applications, proposals, and complaints to authorized state bodies, institutions, and representatives of the people (Article 40)

The Right to Participate in Governance

The right to participate in the governance of the country is exercised either directly or indirectly, through elected representatives. This right guarantees that citizens have the right to vote for and be elected to any body that is elected. In this way, citizens influence the power and decisions made by the government. In this context, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, emphasized the importance of increasing political activity among citizens and organizing free elections: "Our main goal is to fully ensure the rights and freedoms of our citizens, and encourage their active participation in state and public governance" (Sh. Mirziyoyev, speech on electoral system reforms, 2021). This point is reflected in **Article 36** of the Constitution. According to this article:

"Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to participate directly and through their representatives in the governance of society and the state. Such participation is carried out through self-government, holding referendums, democratic formation of state bodies, and public oversight of the activities of state bodies".

The procedure for exercising public oversight over the activities of state bodies is determined by law.

It is also worth noting that significant efforts are being made to establish a fully democratic system of state power. For example, all political parties have the right to nominate their candidates to state representative bodies. This contributes to democratizing the electoral system and allows citizens to elect deputies on a competitive basis. During elections, several candidates may be nominated for a single position, and citizens elect the most suitable candidate. These candidates are, in turn, contributing to the formation of a "multi-party system" in our society.

The legal foundation for political party activities is strengthened in various laws, including the **Law on Public Associations**, the **Law on Political Parties**, the **Law on Political Party Financing**, and the **Law on Guarantees of the Activities of Non-Governmental and Non-Profit Organizations**, as well as in the **Election Code** and other legal documents. These laws ensure the participation of political parties in the development of society.

It is particularly important to note that the constitutional amendments introduced in our Constitution have laid the constitutional foundation for public oversight over the implementation of laws by state and governance bodies. According to these amendments, citizens' involvement in public oversight of the activities of state and public bodies will continue to be developed and

improved. The key point here is that the institution of "public oversight" has been granted constitutional legal status, taking this institution to a qualitatively new level.

The **Law on Public Oversight** defines the subjects and objects of public oversight, its main principles, and the forms of public oversight. It also elaborates on the rights and obligations of the subjects and objects of public oversight, and the procedure for formalizing its results. According to the law, the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, self-governance bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and the mass media have the right to carry out public oversight.

According to Article 37 of our Constitution, "Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have equal rights to enter public service. Restrictions related to entering public service are determined by law".

Public service is an important activity aimed at ensuring citizens' rights and freedoms, as well as providing them with state services. Many citizens aspire to pursue their careers in public service. For this, a strong and stable system must be implemented. Notably, this important political right has already been enshrined in international documents. For example, Article 21 of the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" adopted by the UN on December 10, 1948, states that "everyone has the right to equal access to public service in their country". Additionally, Article 25 of the "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights" emphasizes that every citizen should have the right and opportunity to enter public service without discrimination. Therefore, this political right was established at the constitutional level, ensuring equal, legal, and fair competition in public service, and the recruitment of capable personnel is a key requirement for ensuring quality and efficiency in the work of state bodies and organizations.

According to Article 38 of the Constitution, "Citizens have the right to exercise their social activism through meetings, gatherings, and demonstrations in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Authorities have the right to stop or ban such events only from the perspective of security concerns".

The freedom of meetings, demonstrations, and rallies gives individuals the opportunity to express their opinions and views. This right is also crucial for the government to stay informed about public opinion. It is vital because it allows leaders to gain deeper insights into issues that concern citizens.

A meeting is a peaceful gathering of citizens to express their stance or opinion on social-political events.

A demonstration is a public march or gathering to express political demands.

A gathering is the participation of citizens in a collective discussion of important public matters.

Most importantly, our Constitution recognizes the establishment of civil society institutions and their legal foundation. The principles of cooperation between these institutions and the state have been defined.

In addition, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to join trade unions, political parties, and other public associations, as well as to participate in mass movements. This provision is reflected in **Article 39** of the Constitution. The development of civil society, the emergence of new tasks for the country, the expansion of democratic institutions, and the creation of new mass movements and non-governmental non-profit organizations all necessitate this. The "Strategy of Actions," adopted in 2017, is one of the most important documents in the life of the country, and our future depends on the implementation of the tasks outlined in it.

According to **Article 40** of the Constitution, citizens have the right to apply with requests, proposals, and complaints to state bodies, organizations, and people's reception offices, and this right is also guaranteed by law.

In conclusion, the role of political rights in human life is unparalleled. Political rights, along with strengthening rights and freedoms in our Constitution, also impose great responsibility on citizens. Furthermore, reforms aimed at developing political rights are creating great opportunities for our youth, which is not an exaggeration.

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